

University of Essex
Department of Mathematical Sciences

MA981: DISSERTATION

**A machine learning approach to predicting
the outcome of football matches**

Oliver Parkes
2101301

Supervisor: Dr. Yassir Rabhi

August 24, 2023
Colchester

Abstract

In this dissertation we will present a study which concerns predicting football (soccer) matches using a large dataset. We will employ machine learning methods such as K-Nearest Neighbour, Random Forests, Support Vector Machine and logistic regression in models as a tool for predicting football match outcomes. These methods will be applied to a dataset of football matches from Europe's top five leagues (England, France, Germany, Italy and Spain) from the 2017-18 season up to the 2021-2022 season. The dataset includes various types of match-level statistics like the result, total number of shots and expected goals (xG). The performance of our models are then compared against bookmaker's predictions, as well as leading models that arose from the literature. The study revealed that features related to a team's historic strength and recent form were the most important variables when predicting match outcomes. It also found that a support vector machine trained on the original training set scored the highest accuracy score of 0.5221, whilst a support vector machine trained on data with balanced classes achieved the lowest accuracy of all the models, but the highest F1 score of 0.46. This trend was observed in comparisons between all models where the model trained on data with balanced classes achieved higher F1 score, but lower accuracy scores when compared to the same model trained on the original data with imbalanced classes.

Contents

1	Introduction	8
2	Methodology	12
2.1	K-Nearest Neighbour	12
2.2	Random Forests	13
2.3	Support Vector Machine	15
2.3.1	Support vector machine: One-to-one	15
2.3.2	Support vector machine: One-to-many	16
2.4	Logistic regression	17
2.4.1	Multinomial logistic regression	18
2.5	Feature selection	18
2.6	Model evaluation	18
2.6.1	Accuracy	19
2.6.2	Precision	20
2.6.3	Recall	20
2.6.4	F1 score	21
3	Data preparation	22
3.1	Data sources	22
3.2	Feature engineering	22
3.3	Oversampling	25
4	Data analysis	26
4.1	Exploratory data analysis	26
4.2	Feature selection results	29
4.3	K-Nearest Neighbour	31

4.3.1	Standardisation and normalisation	31
4.3.2	Results	31
4.4	Random Forest	33
4.4.1	Results	33
4.5	Support Vector Machines	35
4.5.1	Results	35
4.6	Logistic Regression	36
4.6.1	Results	36
4.7	Benchmark: Bookmaker's favourites	37
4.7.1	Results	37
5	Conclusions	39
5.1	Model comparisons	39
5.2	Limitations	43
5.3	Future work	44
A	Match data fields	46
B	Prediction data fields	49
C	Odds data fields	52

List of Figures

2.1	Illustration of K-Nearest Neighbour with $k=3$. Left: Test observation (x) being classified as blue by majority vote. Right: Decision boundaries for $k=3$ (James et al. 2021)	12
2.2	Illustration of a Decision Tree (James et al. 2021)	14
2.3	Labelled diagram of a Support Vector Machine for two classes (Kumar et al. 2022)	15
2.4	Illustration of three one-to-one Support Vector Machine for three classes (Baeldung 2022)	16
2.5	Illustration of three one-to-many Support Vector Machine for three classes (Baeldung 2022)	16
2.6	Comparison of linear (left) and logistic (right) regression (James et al. 2021) .	17
3.1	Stacked bar plot of the outcome of matches (by league)	25
4.1	Box plot of the number of goals scored per team per match by league	26
4.2	Boxplot of teams' attack rating going into matches	27
4.3	Boxplot of teams' defensive rating going into matches	28
4.4	Boxplot of teams' form going into matches	29
4.5	Correlation matrix of the predictor variables	30
4.6	Box plots demonstrating variable importance	31
4.7	Scattergraph demonstrating the optimal number for K	32
5.1	Bar chart of accuracy scores achieved by the different models	42

List of Tables

4.1	Confusion matrix for K-Nearest Neighbour's predictions on imbalanced data	32
4.2	Confusion matrix for K-Nearest Neighbour's predictions on balanced data . .	33
4.3	Confusion matrix for Random Forest predictions on imbalanced data	34
4.4	Confusion matrix for Random Forest predictions on balanced data	34
4.5	Confusion matrix for Support Vector Machine predictions on imbalanced data	35
4.6	Confusion matrix for Support Vector Machine predictions on balanced data .	35
4.7	Confusion matrix for Logistic Regression predictions on imbalanced data . .	36
4.8	Confusion matrix for Logistic Regression predictions on balanced data	37
4.9	Confusion matrix for bookmaker's predictions	37
5.1	Accuracy measures for all models	39
A.1	Metadata for bookmaker's odds data	46
B.1	Metadata for the data used in the machine learning models	49
C.1	Metadata for bookmaker's odds data	52

Introduction

Football, also known as soccer across many parts of the globe, is the world's most popular sport (Dvorak et al. 2004). With FIFA, the sport's world governing body, estimating in 2006 that there were 270 million people involved with football worldwide (FIFA n.d.) and Deloitte reporting that the revenue for the world's top clubs reached 9.2 billion euros for the 2021/22 season (Deloitte n.d.), football is a big part of the public consciousness. In academia, football has been the subject of a plethora of research across a range of disciplines looking at topics from physiology and recovery to data based decision making. More recently, academic research has begun to apply machine learning methods to the sport. Rico-Gonzalez et al.'s review highlights the breadth of research being undertaken using machine learning methods, with research spanning from predicting injuries to predicting talent and performance (Rico-Gonzalez et al. 2023). This dissertation will look at the problem of predicting the result of football matches using K-Nearest Neighbour, Random Forests, Support Vector Machines and Logistic Regression.

Predicting the outcome of football matches (win, loss or draw) is not a new field. Reep and Benjamin's seminal paper found that goals were a stochastic variable, although they concluded that they were unable to consistently predict results because 'chance dominates the game' (Reep and Benjamin 1968). At the turn of the century, Dixon and Coles highlighted the various features needed to model a match, with models needing to take into account: the different abilities of both teams; the 'home advantage'; a team's recent form; an account of the teams a team has played recently; and separate measures for offense and defense (Dixon

and Coles 1997). Adding to this, Bilek and Ulas highlight the importance of the opposition's quality, as their models were able to correctly predict the results of games against balanced, stronger and weaker opponents, with an accuracy of 67.9%, 73.9% and 78.4% respectively, whilst their model which did not take into account the opposition's quality achieved an accuracy of 64.8% (Bilek and Ulas 2019). These features tend to form the basis of recent models with Berrar, Lopes and Dubitzky engineering features for attacking performance, defensive performance, recent performances, the strength of the opposition and the home advantage (Berrar, Lopes, and Dubitzky 2019). Recently, academics have competed to see which of them can create the best predictive model using machine learning techniques from a dataset comprising of 216,743 matches from 52 leagues in 35 countries, with the best model achieving an accuracy of 53.88% (Dubitzky et al. 2019). In the main however, research has tended to focus on single domestic leagues. Cui et al.'s approach using a genetic algorithm to predict results in the English Premier league resulted in an accuracy of 56% (Cui et al. 2013), compared with Baboota and Kaur's research where their Random Forests achieved a predictive accuracy of 57% from the same league (Baboota and Kaur 2019). Research that has focused on cup competitions has generally been able to achieve higher accuracy scores. Robberechts and Davis' research looking to predict World Cup matches from 2018 was able to achieve an accuracy of 60.94% (Robberechts and Davis 2018) and Vaswani et al were able to simulate and predict the overall winner of 2019-20 UEFA Champions League (Vaswani et al. 2020). With cup competitions, particularly international tournaments, occurring less frequently and with less matches than domestic leagues, it has not been fully explored how well models apply from one competition to the next. For example, world cups occur every four years, so can you make accurate predictions based of training data from four years ago? Constantinou's research shows that models can predict match outcomes between two teams based on data that neither team participated in (Constantinou 2019). Building on that work, this research will endeavour to separate itself from previous research by training our models on detailed match-level data spanning multiple competitions and multiple years.

This dissertation will explore four Machine Learning techniques (K-Nearest Neighbour, Random Forests, Support Vector Machines and Logistic Regression) as a means of predicting football match outcomes.

K-NN was first developed as classification technique by Fix and Hodges in 1951 (Chirici et al. 2016). K-Nearest Neighbour measures the distance between a point and it's K-Nearest

Neighbours then classifies the point based on a majority vote of its nearest neighbours (Hastie, Tibshirani, and Freidman 2009). K-NN has been successfully applied to a wide range of classification problems, including predicting the outcome of Tottenham Hotspur matches which achieved an accuracy score of 50.58% (Joesph, Fenton, and Neil 2006).

As first described by Breiman in 2001, Random Forests are used in classification problems to generate a group of trees. Each tree casts a vote for the predicted class with the majority vote acting as the classification (Breiman 2001). In Haruna et al's analysis of Premier League matches, they used Random Forests to predict the outcome of football matches and achieved an accuracy of 49.47% (Haruna et al. 2021).

Support Vector Machines seek to find the hyperplane that has the largest distance between data points of both classes. A data point is classified depending on what side of the hyperplane it falls. As ours is a multi-class classification problem (win, draw or loss), we will extend our Support Vector Machine by using either the one-versus-one classification or the one-versus-all classification (James et al. 2021).

Logistic Regression is a model used to predict a categorical variable by estimating the probability of an event taking place using the logistic function. Despite the logistic function having been developed in the 1840s the logistic model was not first developed until 100 years later (Cramer 2002), with multinomial logistic regression then being introduced in the late 1960s (Theil 1969).

With the proliferation of more advanced publicly available match data, the models will be applied to match-level data from Europe's top five leagues: England, France, Germany, Italy and Spain from the 2017-18 up to the 2021-2022 season. The data was scraped from [FBref.com](https://fbref.com) on the 5 May 2023 using the CRAN package `worldfootballR`. In total it contains data from 10,939 matches (21,878 observations) with 54 variables, including basic match-level information like teams, league and score, and more detailed match-level information like expected goals (xG), number of progressive actions and the number of ball touches. FBref collects their data in partnership with third party suppliers such as the Data Sports Group and Opta.

The performance of the models will be compared to the leading models in the literature, as well as bookmaker odds. Stubinger and Knoll's research highlighted that it was possible to create models which predicted matches more accurately than book makers, who tended to have an accuracy 54.49% (Stubinger and Knoll 2018). This research is not focused on

economic gains however, but is instead looking to see how well different machine learning methods compare against leading predictions in both industry and academia.

In the following chapters we will explore K-Nearest Neighbour, Random Forests, Support Vector Machines and Logistic Regression in further depth, examine our data and compare the results of our models against leading models in academia and industry.

Methodology

In this chapter we will explore the machine learning techniques used for classifying the results of the matches. Specifically: K-Nearest Neighbour, Random Forests, Support Vector Machines and Logistic Regression, as well as the methods used to evaluate them.

2.1 K-Nearest Neighbour

K-Nearest Neighbour (K-NN) is a supervised machine learning technique which can be used to solve both classification and regression problems. It works on the premise that observations of the same classification are likely to have similar features, so a query is classified based on its k neighbours.

Figure 2.1: Illustration of K-Nearest Neighbour with $k=3$. Left: Test observation (x) being classified as blue by majority vote. Right: Decision boundaries for $k=3$ (James et al. 2021)

As illustrated by figure 2.1, test observations are mapped in the training set and classified

by the most common classification of their k neighbours. K-Nearest Neighbour falls under the lazy learning umbrella, because no calculations are done until the test data is introduced to the training data (Zhou 2021). The full algorithm can be given as:

1. Select a value for k
2. Calculate the euclidean distance between the query (test-data observation) and every observation in the training set.
3. Select k observations nearest to the query.
4. Classify the query based on the modal classification of it's k-nearest neighbours, with ties being decided randomly.

With the Euclidean distance is given as:

$$d_{(i)} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - y_i)^2} \quad (2.1.1)$$

Where x and y are two points in Euclidean n -space, x_i and y_i are Euclidean vectors and n is n -space.

Before conducting K-Nearest Neighbour, our dataset will undergo standardisation. This means all numeric variables are standardised and given a mean of 0 and standard deviation of 1. This is essential for producing meaningful predictions, as the effect of large scale variables on the euclidean distance is much greater than variables on smaller scales (James et al. 2021). In terms of finding the optimal value of k , K-Nearest Neighbour will be run multiple times with different values of k to see which value predicts with the highest accuracy.

2.2 Random Forests

Random Forests are a supervised machine learning technique created by combining multiple *uncorrelated* Decision Trees (Hastie, Tibshirani, and Freidman 2009). Decision Trees are used in both classification and regressions problems and make their predictions by repeatedly splitting the data into two sets. Decision Trees are prone to overfitting, so a tree depth is usually specified. To optimise the split, decision trees use one of two measures:

- Gini index, a measure of node purity with low value indicating that a node is predominantly made up of observations from a single class. Defined by James et al. as (James et al. 2021):

$$G = \sum_{k=1}^K \hat{p}_{mk}(1 - \hat{p}_{mk}) \quad (2.2.1)$$

- Entropy, another measure of node purity with low values indicating that a node is predominantly made up of observations from a single class. Defined by James et al. as (James et al. 2021):

$$D = -\sum_{k=1}^K \hat{p}_{mk} \log \hat{p}_{mk} \quad (2.2.2)$$

Where \hat{p}_{mk} represents the proportion of training observations in the m^{th} region that are from the k^{th} class. For splits on gini impurity, the algorithm seeks to maximise the gini gain and for splits on entropy the algorithm seeks to maximise information gain.

Figure 2.2: Illustration of a Decision Tree (James et al. 2021)

In Random Forests, the Decision Trees also bootstrap (randomly sample with replacement) the observations, so each tree is a subset of all the training observations. The Decision Trees are also given a random sample of m variables to choose to make their splits from, with the default value of m being the square root of the number of variables, although random forests should be run with different values m to find the optimal value (James et al. 2021). By making the split on a random subset of variables, Random Forests ensure that Decision Trees are at the most only weakly correlated and make their own models more accurate by combining predictions from multiple models. The algorithm for Random Forests can be given as:

1. Select a bootstrapped sample of the training set.

2. Construct a decision tree from the sample where splits are made on a random subset of all the variables in the training set.
3. Collect the class vote from each tree.
4. Classify the query based on the majority vote from all trees.

2.3 Support Vector Machine

Support Vector Machine is a machine learning technique which can be used for both regression and classification problems. They look to separate data into categories using a hyperplane, with data being classified by which side of the plane it lands on.

Figure 2.3: Labelled diagram of a Support Vector Machine for two classes (Kumar et al. 2022)

As demonstrated in figure 2.3, the optimal hyperplane is found by maximising the margin between classes in the training data. To avoid overfitting and to allow for better application to the test dataset, Support Vector Machines allow for the misclassification of some training observations. By their nature, hyperplanes cannot separate data into more than two classes which is an issue in this dissertation because we have three classifiers: win, draw or loss. To deal with this problem, Support Vector Machines can be approached in two ways: one-to-one or one-to-many.

2.3.1 Support vector machine: One-to-one

One method of dealing with multiple classification in Support Vector Machines is to use the one-to-one approach which runs multiple Support Vector Machines that look to separate

one class from one other class and ignores all other classes. For example, for classes A, B and C, there would be three hyperplanes: one dividing class A from class B but ignoring C, one dividing class A from class C but ignoring B, and one dividing class B from class C but ignoring A. More concisely, and as illustrated in figure 2.4, the one-to-one approach would need $\frac{n(n-1)}{2}$ Support Vector Machines (Baeldung 2022).

Figure 2.4: Illustration of three one-to-one Support Vector Machine for three classes (Baeldung 2022)

2.3.2 Support vector machine: One-to-many

One-to-many, or one-to-rest, is another method which looks to deal with multiple classifications in Support Vector Machines. It works by separating one class from all others. For example, for classes A, B and C, there would be three hyperplanes: one dividing class A from class B and C, one dividing class B from class A and C, and one dividing class C from class A and B. More concisely, and as illustrated in figure 2.5, the one-to-many approach would need n Support Vector Machines (Baeldung 2022).

Figure 2.5: Illustration of three one-to-many Support Vector Machine for three classes (Baeldung 2022)

2.4 Logistic regression

Figure 2.6: Comparison of linear (left) and logistic (right) regression (James et al. 2021)

Logistic regression is a statistical model used in classification problems that estimates to probability that the response variable belongs to a binary categorical variable i.e. if a stock will rise or fall. Because binary categorical variables are often coded as a 0 or a 1, if we use a multiple linear regression model, given as:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_i x_i \quad (2.4.1)$$

we find that the probability of the response variable belonging to a category can be greater than 1 or less than 0. To counter this problem, we use the logistic function to guarantee all probability values fall between 0 and 1. The formula for multiple logistic regression can be given as:

$$\text{logit}(\pi_i) = \log\left(\frac{\pi_i}{1 - \pi_i}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_i x_i \quad (2.4.2)$$

As seen in figure 2.6, because of the logit function when plotting a logistic regression you plot an 's' shape as compared to a line in a linear regression. Another feature that separates logistic regression from linear is that whilst in a linear regression β_i gives the change to the dependent variable associated with a one-unit change to the independent variable, in a logistic regression β_i gives a change to the log odds associated with the dependent variable. To estimate the regression coefficients (β) in a logistic model, we use the maximum likelihood estimate which seeks to find the estimates for β which when used in the model are close to 1 for categorical variables which are labelled 1 and close to 0 for categorical variables labelled as 0. For example, if a stock was predicted to fall we would want β estimates used in the

model to equal close to 0, but if it was predicted to rise we would want β estimates used in the model close to 1.

2.4.1 Multinomial logistic regression

In this dissertation we are seeking to classify the results of football matches so the response variable has more than two response variables, in this case three: win, draw or loss. To deal with multi-class classification, we will use a technique called multinomial logistic regression. Multinomial logistic regression runs similarly to binomial logistic regression but is run several times with one class acting as the *baseline*. For example, with three classifications: A, B and C, and with A as your baseline the regression would be run twice: A vs B and A vs C. Odds are then compared that an observation will either be the baseline or the other classification. The choice of baseline is unimportant as the model's predictions remain the same, but should be kept in mind when interpreting results as your comparing the odds of an observation being the baseline or one other classification, not the full set of classes.

2.5 Feature selection

Although our model followed the framework set out in Dixon and Coles' model by having variables for a team's strength, form, attacking and defensive abilities, the data did undergo collinearity tests and a process of feature selection. The collinearity tests we undertook were plotting the correlation coefficients of the predictor variables in a correlation matrix. The coefficient values were then reviewed for values greater than 0.7, which is when a model's ability to predict becomes negatively affected (Dormann et al. 2013). The predictor variables were then reviewed to see if they needed to be reduced further. This was done by applying the Boruta algorithm on them, which is a wrapper-method feature selection algorithm that seeks to find all relevant variables (Kursa and Rudnicki 2010). The algorithm was applied using the Boruta package in R and the results can be found in 4.2.

2.6 Model evaluation

To evaluate and compare the different models, we will look at four different measures: accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score. As we have a multi-class classification, other than

accuracy, we calculate each evaluation metric per class - home win, away win or draw. In the context of this study:

- a true positive (TP) would be cases where the predicted class is the same as the actual class and it is also the class we are evaluating. For example if we're measuring the precision of draws, a true positive would be where we've predicted draw and the actual result was a draw.
- a true negative (TN) would be cases where the predicted class is the same as the actual class for classes we are not evaluating. For example if we're measuring the precision of draws, a true negative would be where we've predicted a home win and the actual result was a home win.
- a false positive (FP) would be cases where the predicted class is not the same as the actual class, but it is the same as the class we are evaluating. For example if we're measuring the precision of draws, a false positive would be where we've predicted draw and the actual result was a different class.
- a false negative (FN) would be cases where the predicted class is not the same as the actual class for classes we are not evaluating. For example if we're measuring the precision of draws, a false negative would be where we've predicted an away win and the actual result was a home win.

2.6.1 Accuracy

Accuracy, or classification accuracy, is the proportion of correctly predicted classes against all predictions. Accuracy can take a value equal to or between zero and one, with zero highlighting that no predictions were correct and one demonstrating that all predictions were correct. It is not always a suitable evaluation metric because it can be heavily skewed by class imbalances. It is calculated by:

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + FN + TN + FP} \quad (2.6.1)$$

where:

TP = True Positives

TN = True Negatives

FN = False Negatives

FP = False Positives

2.6.2 Precision

Precision is a measure which looks at of all the predictions for that class how many were right. They are calculated class-by-class in a multi-class classification problem, so if you were evaluating home wins in the model you would see how many of the home wins that were correctly predicted against how many home wins were predicted. Like accuracy, it has a range of zero to one and it's formula is given by:

$$Precision(x) = \frac{TP(x)}{TP(x) + FP(x)} \quad (2.6.2)$$

where:

TP = True Positives

FP = False Positives

x = the class being evaluated

2.6.3 Recall

Recall is a metric which looks at of all the actual results belonging to that class, how many were predicted. For example, out of all the actual home wins in the test set, how many were actually predicted. It has a range of zero to one and is calculated by:

$$Recall(x) = \frac{TP(x)}{TP(x) + FN(x)} \quad (2.6.3)$$

where:

TP = True Positives

FN = False Negatives

x = the class being evaluated

2.6.4 F1 score

F1 score is a harmonisation of precision and recall and looks to tell you how good the model is at predicting results correctly. It has a range of zero to one with higher scores indicating better models. It is calculated by:

$$F1(x) = \frac{2 \times Precision(x) \times Recall(x)}{Precision(x) + Recall(x)} \quad (2.6.4)$$

where:

x = the class being evaluated

As our problem is a multi-class classification problem, we'll be taking the macro averaged F1 score to compare models. This means we'll take the mean F1 score of all classes per model. Unlike accuracy, F1 scores are not influenced by class imbalances, so in some cases is the more suitable metric to use.

Data preparation

3.1 Data sources

Data on bookmaker's odds were downloaded from football-data.co.uk with a single file relating to a single season for a single league. These files were then combined into a single dataset containing bookmaker's odds on every match from the top-flight leagues of England, France, Germany, Italy and Spain from 2017-2022. Match-level data was accessed through FBref's API using the worldfootballR CRAN package and contained many unnecessary variables, whilst also lacking many fields that were needed to predict the result of matches. The dataset itself contained match-level information per team per match for every match in the top-flight leagues of England, France, Germany, Italy and Spain from 2017-2022. This meant that every match had two rows: one containing figures related to the home teams performance and one containing figures related to the away teams performance.

3.2 Feature engineering

Despite the availability of sports data, a lot of work was needed to engineer suitable features to implement predictive machine learning techniques. For the dataset containing bookmakers odds, simple alterations were made to the field names to ensure they matched those in the dataset containing match-level figures. Data types were also changed to suit the data the field contained i.e. the field containing the day matches were played was changed to a data

variable. This ensured that filters and functions would then work when applied in the data analysis. Team names were also changed to match the team names in the dataset containing match-level figures (i.e. Stoke was changed to Stoke City) and a new field was created which flagged the bookmaker's favourite for a given match. This was done by comparing the three fields for the odds of a home win, away win or draw, taking the lowest figure and assigning the character string 'Home', 'Away' or 'Draw' depending on the field with the lowest number.

The process of engineering match-level features was more complicated. Initially the data types of field names were changed to suit the data in that field. Additionally, fields with the data type *integer* were changed to *numeric* as many of the libraries used to implement machine learning algorithms were not compatible with the *integer* data type. Rows with NAs were removed from the dataset, which amounted to the removal of 25 matches: 23 French league matches from March 2020 to April 2020. 1 Italian league match from 2020 and 1 German match from 2022. The NAs were due to some statistics not being collected for those matches. To create a dataset suitable to predict the outcomes of football matches, the following features were engineered:

1. A new field was coded stating whether the match was won by the home, away team or a draw. This was made by calculating the difference between the home score and the away score and assigning a character related to the outcome: *h* for home win, *a* for away win and *d* for draw.
2. A new field was created which states either the name of the team who won or draw. This was created by looking up the data from the field created previously and returning either the name of the home or away team, or in the case of draw stating 'Draw'.
3. A new field was created which assigned points to the team depending on the result of the match. Three points were assigned to the team who won, one point was assigned for draws or 0 for a loss. This was assigned by comparing the team name associated with the data in the row to field which states the name of the team which won. Three points were assigned if they matched, one point if the name of the team which won was 'Draw' and zero points if neither of those conditions were met.
4. A variable which acted as a proxy for team's strength was created. This field sums all of a teams points over the five year period (2017-2022).

5. A proxy variable for a team's form was also created. This field sums the points of their last 5 matches irrespective of whether they played home or away.
6. A proxy variable for a team's attacking prowess was created by summing the expected goals¹ of a team over their last five matches.
7. A proxy variable for a team's defensive prowess was created by summing the expected goals of their opposition for their last five matches.
8. These created fields were then split into home and away depending on the whether the team who the row represented was playing home or away. The rows on the dataset were then merged so the data went from representing match-level information per team per match (two observations per match) to just representing match-level information per match (one observation per match).

The features engineered in items 4, 5, 6 and 7 were created as proxies for the different abilities of both teams, an account of a team's recent form and a measure of a team's attacking threat and a team's defensive abilities, all of which are described as essential features for predicting the outcomes of matches by Dixon and Coles (Dixon and Coles 1997). Expected goals was used as a proxy measure for a team's attacking and defensive abilities as it is a measure of the quality of chances a team creates or concedes rather than a measure of quantity. Had we used shots or shots on target, teams who take many speculative shots with low probabilities of scoring will have higher attacking scores than teams who work fewer higher quality chances, but likely score more goals.

Once this pre-processing was completed we were left with three datasets:

1. Matches. A dataset with match-level statistics for home and away teams which is described in detail in appendix A.
2. Predictions. A dataset used in the machine learning algorithms. It is a reduced version of matches, which only contains variables used in the machine learning models. It is split into training and testing subsets with the training subset containing data from

¹Expected goals, or xG, is a measure of the quality of shot based on different characteristics like the location of a shot and positioning of defenders and the goal keeper. A single shot can have a value between zero and one with zero indicating a shot is certain not to score. If a team finished a match with an expected goals of 2.1 you would have expected them to score at least two goals from the shots they had (FBref 2023).

the 2017-2018 to the 2020-2021 seasons and the test subset containing data from the 2021-2022 season. It is described in detail in appendix B.

3. Odds data. A dataset comprised of bookmaker's odds for matches which is described in detail in appendix C.

3.3 Oversampling

Figure 3.1: Stacked bar plot of the outcome of matches (by league)

As illustrated by figure 3.1, there is some imbalance in our dataset with home wins being the dominant class. Unequal distribution of classes, in this case 43% home wins, 32% away wins and 25% draws, can lead to a reduction in accuracy of Machine Learning algorithms. To observe the affect of the unequal distribution of classes, all machine learning methods will be run twice: once with the original training subset and again with an oversampled version of the subset. Equal distribution of classes was achieved by using the `upSample` function in R's `caret` package and applying it to the training subset. The function works by leaving the original data intact, but adds additional samples to minority classes with replacement (rdrr.io 2023). Oversampling, rather than undersampling, was chosen as the method to balance the classes, as it does not reduce the number of observations in our training data.

Data analysis

In the following chapter we will explore the features of the dataset, consider the results of our feature selection and review the results of the different machine learning models used when predicting the result of football matches.

4.1 Exploratory data analysis

Figure 4.1: Box plot of the number of goals scored per team per match by league

Exploring the match-level data in figure 4.1 we can see each team scores between zero and two goals with a median of one across all leagues. That means in every match across all five

leagues 75% of the teams scored between zero and two goals. With so few goals being scored by teams and thus little separation in the score between two teams, it is easy to see one of the main difficulties in predicting the outcome of football matches: random or low-probability events can have a massive impact on the final outcome. The findings from 2017-2022 are also in line with what Reep and Benjamin observed in the 1960s with 'chance dominating the game' and making predicting the classification of results so difficult (Reep and Benjamin 1968). It also shows that the number of goals scored is very similar across the leagues which suggests that all five leagues are relatively comparable and allows us to compile a training data set consisting of matches from all five leagues.

Following Dixon and Coles' framework, we coded proxy variables for: the different abilities of both teams, a teams recent form, and separate measures for both attacking and defending. The variable TeamStrength acts as a proxy for the ability of a team by looking at how good a team has been historically. Across this dataset, teams with a higher TeamStrength variable going into the match win 51.98% of the time. This can best be demonstrated when you explore Bayern Munich's results (5th highest in total wins in the period) against Greuther, Nurnberg and Paderborn (1st, 2nd and 3rd lowest in total wins across the period. Across the period Bayern take 16 out of a total of 18 points from teams in the bottom five for total wins. This is despite the fact that Bayern had a similar form to their opposition in some of these matches - in Bayern's 4-1 home win against Greuther Bayern had accrued 9 points in their last five matches, whilst Greuther had accrued 8.

Figure 4.2: Boxplot of teams' attack rating going into matches

In figure 4.2 we see that observations for a team's attack rating are similar across all five leagues, although teams in the German Bundesliga have slightly higher attack scores (caused by having higher expected goals per game) on average when compared to teams in England, France, Italy and Spain's top division. This is also seen in figure 4.1 where the lower and upper quartiles in the box plot cover one goal to two, whereas for the other leagues the lower and upper quartiles cover from zero goals to two. Similarly for goals scored, this figure highlights that there are similarities across all five leagues and we should feel comfortable combining match-level data from the English, French, German, Italian and Spanish top divisions. When judging the outcome solely by comparing the two team's attacking rating, the team heading into the match with the higher attacking rating tends to win 46.75% of the time, which helps to demonstrate its importance as a predictor.

Figure 4.3: Boxplot of teams' defensive rating going into matches

Figure 4.3 illustrates a team's defensive rating going into matches in the form of a boxplot. Expectedly, it is very similar to figure 4.2. This is due to a team's defence rating being calculated from expected goals conceded - the inverse of a team's attacking rating. In the defensive ratings the German teams have slightly higher ratings (so worse defenses) when compared to the other leagues. Despite that, they are all similar to a degree where you would feel comfortable combining matches from separate leagues to train the machine learning models. The importance of a team's defensive rating as a predictor can be highlighted when predicting a result solely from the two team's defensive rating, the team with the better defence score tended to win 47.68% of the time.

Figure 4.4: Boxplot of teams' form going into matches

Figure 4.4 depicts a team's form (points gained from their previous five matches). Similarly to the previous box plots, team's form is very similar across all five leagues with the English, French, German and Spanish leagues all having identical plots. Again, this allows us to be comfortable combining all leagues in our training and test data sets. A team's form also appears to be an important indicator when predicting the outcome of a game. In this data set, teams going into the match with the better form would go on to win 45.50% of the time.

4.2 Feature selection results

The results of the collinearity tests are illustrated in figure 4.5. Although there are some correlations, there are no correlation coefficients that exceed the threshold of 0.7 or -0.7. This satisfies the assumption that collinearity does not exist amongst these predictor variables, so we do not have to look to reduce the number of variables further. Unsurprisingly there are correlations between team strength, form, attack and defensive. This is expected as better teams will have higher strength and form ratings and have likely achieved this by being stronger attacking teams and more solid defensively. This is observed for both home and away teams and, as expected, there are no correlations between variables associated with the home team and variables associated with the away team.

Figure 4.5: Correlation matrix of the predictor variables

Reviewing the results of the boruta algorithm in figure 4.6, we can see that when trying to predict the outcome of football matches all of our predictor variables achieved higher importance scores than the shadowMax and thus pass the threshold for being important. Interestingly, team strength for both home and away teams was scored as the most important, whilst metrics for form, attack and defence all scored very similarly. This expands on the findings in the exploratory data analysis where it was shown that teams with the higher team strength going into the match tend to win 51.98% of the time. Furthermore, in the boruta algorithm variables related to form, attacking quality and defensive quality all scored very similarly and also had similar win percentages when you compared one of those variables for the home and away team.

Figure 4.6: Box plots demonstrating variable importance

4.3 K-Nearest Neighbour

4.3.1 Standardisation and normalisation

Before the K-Nearest Neighbour algorithm was run, a process of standardisation and normalisation was undertaken on the data. Using the `preProcess` function in R, as part of the `train` function in R's `caret` package, data was recoded to have a value between zero and one. This was achieved by subtracting the mean of the predictor from each predictor's value and then dividing by the standard deviation of the predictor (RDocumentation 2023). This was done to reduce the scale of all variables to avoid variables with larger scales from having more of an influence over the model, because of their greater euclidean distances.

4.3.2 Results

Before predictions were made, the optimal number for K had to be found. To find the optimal number, the K-Nearest Neighbour algorithm was run multiple times on the training data to find which number of K gave the highest accuracy score. As demonstrated in figure 4.7, the optimal number for K is 84, however any number for K over 60 gave a similar figure for accuracy. With K equal to 84 the model was run again, this time on the test dataset with its results demonstrated in table 4.1.

Figure 4.7: Scattergraph demonstrating the optimal number for K

		Actual		
		Away win	Draw	Home win
Predicted	Away win	295	153	138
	Draw	24	20	30
	Home win	236	285	581

Table 4.1: Confusion matrix for K-Nearest Neighbour's predictions on imbalanced data

The results of the K-Nearest Neighbour are described in table 4.1. Predictions using the K-Nearest Neighbour algorithm resulted in an accuracy of 0.5085, so the algorithm was able to accurately predict the result of the test data 50.85% of the time. For home wins it achieved good results for precision (0.53) and very high results for recall (0.78). In practice this means that for the test set, 52% of the predictions for home win were correct and it predicted 78% of all the actual home wins. It did not score as well predicting away wins where it earned a precision of 0.5 and a recall of 0.53. Overall the model achieved a macro-averaged F1 score of 0.40. On face value this seems like a good result, however when you look at the model's recall for predicting draws it performs very poorly with a score 0.04. This means that the algorithm

only successfully predicted 4% of all the actual draws. This low score is likely down to the imbalanced classes in the data. To see if the model could be improved upon, it was run again but this time with a training data set that had been balanced so there were equal number of all classes.

		Actual		
		Away win	Draw	Home win
Predicted	Away win	229	139	176
	Draw	143	121	180
	Home win	183	198	393

Table 4.2: Confusion matrix for K-Nearest Neighbour's predictions on balanced data

The results of the K-Nearest Neighbour model run on balanced data can be seen in table 4.2. This model achieved a lower overall accuracy (0.4217) compared to the imbalanced model, but achieved the same macro-averaged F1 score (0.40). It achieved similar precision scores for home wins, away wins and draws, but the big difference came in the recall for draws. The recall for draw rose from 0.04 on the imbalanced model to 0.26 on the balanced data, however this came at the cost of the recall for home wins where it fell from 0.78 to 0.52. As you would expect, the balanced model was better at predicting the minority class (draws), but overall the imbalanced model was far superior at predicting home wins and away wins. Deciding which of the K-Nearest Neighbour models are better would depend on your reason for applying it. You would choose the model trained on imbalanced data if you were looking to either predict the result of football matches or predict how many home teams would win, as it has higher overall scores for overall accuracy and a stronger recall for home wins, but you would chose the balanced data set if you were interested in predicting draws.

4.4 Random Forest

4.4.1 Results

The Random Forest model achieved an accuracy of 0.5006, so it was able to accurately predict the result of half the matches in the test set. It achieved high scores for precision and recall

		Actual		
		Away win	Draw	Home win
Predicted	Away win	279	157	126
	Draw	54	41	61
	Home win	222	260	562

Table 4.3: Confusion matrix for Random Forest predictions on imbalanced data

when predicting home wins, 0.54 and 0.75 respectively. The model was also able to predict away wins moderately well achieving a precision and a recall of 0.5. Like the K-Nearest Neighbour it struggled to predict draws, achieving a precision 0.26 and a recall of 0.09. This meant that of all the actual draws it was only able to predict 9% of them and of all the matches it predicted to be draws only 26% were. The model achieved a macro-averaged F1 score of 0.42. To see if the Random Forest model could be improved upon, the model was run again on the same test set but this time with balanced classes in the training set.

		Actual		
		Away win	Draw	Home win
Predicted	Away win	288	152	143
	Draw	92	82	114
	Home win	175	224	492

Table 4.4: Confusion matrix for Random Forest predictions on balanced data

Table 4.4 contains the results of the Random Forest model trained using balanced training set. This model had an accuracy slightly lower (0.4892) compared to the Random Forest trained on the imbalanced training set (0.5), however its precision and recall scores for home wins and away wins were either the same or only slightly reduced. The balanced Random Forest was able to improve recall when predicting away wins (0.52) and draws with a significant rise from 0.09 in the imbalanced model to 0.28. The precision metric for draws did remain similar in both the imbalanced and the balanced model (0.26 and 0.28 respectively). The model trained on balanced data was able to slightly improve the macro-averaged F1 score rising from 0.42 in the imbalanced model to 0.44. This increase was due to

the improved performance predicting draws and only a slight deterioration in performance when predicting home wins, leading to a much more well-rounded model.

4.5 Support Vector Machines

4.5.1 Results

		Actual		
		Away win	Draw	Home win
Predicted	Away win	287	148	124
	Draw	148	34	28
	Home win	122	276	599

Table 4.5: Confusion matrix for Support Vector Machine predictions on imbalanced data

The results of the Support Vector Machine model can be seen in table 4.5. The confusion matrix shows the model produced an accuracy of 0.5221 with a precision score of 0.60 and a recall of 0.8 when predicting home wins. This means it managed to predict 80% of all the actual home wins in the test set. It was not as good at predicting away wins, where it scored a precision score of 0.51 and recall score of 0.52. Like other imbalanced models, it struggled predicting the minority class, where it scored a precision of 0.16 and a recall of 0.07 predicting draws. Overall the model scored a macro-averaged F1 score of 0.42.

		Actual		
		Away win	Draw	Home win
Predicted	Away win	275	155	141
	Draw	171	172	239
	Home win	109	131	369

Table 4.6: Confusion matrix for Support Vector Machine predictions on balanced data

The confusion matrix in table 4.6 shows the results of the model when it was re-trained on a balanced data set and applied to the same test set as the imbalanced model. The two

big drops in performance came in the model's overall accuracy score where it dropped from 0.5331 to 0.4631 and the recall for home wins where it dropped from 0.8 to 0.49. The model trained on balance data did see big improvements to its precision and recall for draws where it rose from 0.16 to 0.3 and from 0.07 to 0.38 respectively. The overall macro-averaged F1 score also rose from 0.42 to 0.46, which suggests the model improved as a whole. Deciding on which of the two Support Vector Machine models is best would depend again on its use case. The model trained on imbalanced data was able to predict home wins and away wins better than the balanced model, but the balanced model was able to classify draws much more accurately.

4.6 Logistic Regression

4.6.1 Results

		Actual		
		Away win	Draw	Home win
Predicted	Away win	326	181	164
	Draw	2	2	1
	Home win	227	275	584

Table 4.7: Confusion matrix for Logistic Regression predictions on imbalanced data

The results for the logistic regression trained on imbalanced data can be seen in the confusion matrix in table 4.7. The logistic regression model scored a precision of 0.54 and a recall of 0.78 when predicting home wins and a precision of 0.49 and recall of 0.59 when predicting away wins. The model achieved a macro-averaged F1 score 0.3 and an overall accuracy of 0.5176. Similar to the other models, it has performed extremely poorly at predicting draws. Despite scoring 0.4 for precision, the model scored 0.00 for recall when predicting draws and only predicted five draws total. This means that of the five draws predicted, two were correct but only predicted less than 1% of all actual draws. The precision score was likely inflated due to the low number of draws predicted. Unlike the other models this is likely down to two factors: the class imbalance and logistic regression primarily being a binomial

classification technique. It has to be adapted to work on multinomial classification problems.

		Actual		
		Away win	Draw	Home win
Predicted	Away win	331	186	164
	Draw	92	102	131
	Home win	132	176	454

Table 4.8: Confusion matrix for Logistic Regression predictions on balanced data

Reviewing the results of the logistic regression trained on the balanced training data set in table 4.8, we can see a large improvement in the model's ability to predict draws with the recall rising from 0.00 to 0.22. There is also a rise in the precision of home win predictions with it moving from 0.54 to 0.6 and a rise in the recall of away wins with it moving from 0.59 to 0.6. The model's macro-averaged F1 score rose from 0.38 to 0.46, although this come at a cost of the recall of home wins falling from 0.78 to 0.61. The model's overall accuracy also fell from 0.5176 to 0.5016.

4.7 Benchmark: Bookmaker's favourites

4.7.1 Results

		Actual		
		Away win	Draw	Home win
Predicted	Away win	1599	763	689
	Draw	0	1	0
	Home win	1238	1510	3224

Table 4.9: Confusion matrix for bookmaker's predictions

Reviewing Bet365's favourite outcome in the dataset containing betting odd's data, the confusion matrix in table 4.9 was produced. *Actual* is the actual result and *predicted* is which outcome Bet365 had as their favourite (offered the lowest returns) going into the match.

Their model performed particularly well when predicting home wins, achieving a recall of 0.82 for home wins meaning that they predicted 82% of every home win. Their model also achieved an accuracy of 0.5346 and a macro-averaged F1 score of 0.39. Like our models which were trained on imbalanced data, Bet365's model performed poorly when predicting draws and achieved a recall of 0.00 meaning they were able to predict less than 1% of all draws across the period. They only predicted one draw across all of matches from England, France, Germany, Italy and Spain's top division from the 2017-2018 to the 2021-2022 season, which was predicted correctly. This gave them a precision score of 1, which is likely a product of the low number of predicted draws rather than a strength of their model.

Conclusions

In this chapter we will compare all of the models we have run amongst themselves and leading models that arose in the literature. We will then explore the limitations of this research and discuss how future work could build upon these findings.

5.1 Model comparisons

Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision			Recall			F1 score			Avg. F1 score
		H	A	D	H	A	D	H	A	D	
K-NN (original)	50.85	0.53	0.50	0.27	0.78	0.53	0.04	0.61	0.51	0.07	0.40
K-NN (balanced)	42.17	0.51	0.42	0.27	0.52	0.41	0.26	0.46	0.41	0.32	0.40
Random Forest (original)	50.06	0.54	0.50	0.26	0.75	0.50	0.09	0.60	0.50	0.15	0.42
Random Forest (balanced)	48.92	0.55	0.49	0.28	0.66	0.52	0.28	0.56	0.50	0.26	0.44
SVM (original)	52.21	0.60	0.51	0.16	0.80	0.52	0.07	0.62	0.51	0.12	0.42
SVM (balanced)	46.31	0.61	0.48	0.30	0.49	0.50	0.38	0.48	0.49	0.42	0.46
Log. Regression (original)	51.76	0.54	0.49	0.40	0.78	0.59	0.00	0.60	0.54	0.00	0.38
Log. Regression (balanced)	50.16	0.60	0.49	0.31	0.61	0.60	0.22	0.54	0.54	0.30	0.46
Bookmaker's odds	53.46	0.54	0.52	1.00	0.82	0.56	0.00	0.64	0.54	0.00	0.39

Table 5.1: Accuracy measures for all models

Comparing all of our models we can see that the support vector machine had the greatest accuracy score, which was only slightly lower than that of the bookmakers. We also observed that the models trained on imbalanced data achieved greater accuracies than those trained

on a data set with equal classes. This is likely down to two factors:

- the balanced models' improved ability to predict draws was less than the detrimental effect on their ability to predict home wins resulting in a lower overall accuracy.
- accuracy, as a metric, is not as useful when there is a class imbalance. Accuracy metrics tend to be greater when there is a class imbalance and the model is good at predicting the dominant class. For example if you were predicting whether a patient had a 1 in 100 illness and your model always predicted no, it would have an accuracy of 99%. The class imbalances aren't as severe in those models, but this is likely why we're observing higher accuracies in the model's trained on imbalanced data.

In terms of precision, other than the two K-Nearest Neighbour models, all models regardless of how they were trained achieved equal to or higher precision scores for home wins compared to the benchmark. No models however scored higher in precision when compared to the benchmark in away wins or draws. This means, bar the K-Nearest Neighbour algorithm, we can have greater confidence in home win predictions coming from our models when compared to the benchmark, but less confidence in draws and away wins. Other than in the Support Vector Machine models (precision of draws rose in the balanced model) and Logistic Regression (precision of draws fell in the balanced model), training the model on imbalanced or balanced data had very little effect on precision scores across all classes.

None of our models achieved a greater recall score for home wins when compared to the benchmark, however they all scored greater than or equal to the benchmark in predicting draws and both logistic regression models scored higher when classifying away wins. The Support Vector Machine model trained on the balanced training set performed especially well when classifying draws compared to the benchmark. It achieved a recall score of 0.38 compared to the benchmark's recall score 0.00. This means that of all draws, Bet365 predicted less than 1% of them whilst the Support Vector Machine was able to correctly classify 38% of all draws in the test set.

Models struggled greatly when comparing the F1 scores of individual classes to the benchmark. No models achieved a F1 score greater than or equal to the bookmaker's F1 score for predicting home wins and only both logistic regression models were able to equal the bookmaker's F1 score for predicting away wins. Where our models did perform well was with the F1 score for draws where they all scored greater than or equal to the benchmark's F1

score for predicting draws. Again, the Support Vector Machine trained on balanced classes which scored 0.42 was able to outperform the benchmark model which scored 0.00 - the greatest difference across all metrics. All models, bar the logistic regression trained on the imbalanced training set, had higher macro-averaged F1 scores compared to the benchmark, with the logistic regression and the support vector machine trained on balanced classes having the greatest scores at 0.46.

In general, models trained on imbalanced data sets were better at predicting the dominant class, but were poor at predicting draws. By balancing the classes in the training set we were able to improve recall for the minority class (draws), but saw very little improvement in precision. We also observed all models trained on balanced data improve upon the F1 score at the cost of lower accuracy when compared to the equivalent model trained on the original imbalanced data. It is not possible to define which model is the best without first defining why the model is being applied in the first place. If you were purely interested in predicting the correct result the greatest number of times you would use the support vector machine trained on the imbalanced training data. Instead, if you were interested in using these models to aid a gambling strategy you may be better off using the support vector machine trained on the balanced training set. This is due to the fact that the logistic regression only achieved a slightly lower accuracy of 0.5221 when compared to the bookmakers (0.5346) and is unlikely to result in any economic returns over the course of a season. Instead, a strategy of betting on draws - which were identified as a weakness in the bookmaker's model (recall of 0.00) - using predictions made by the support vector machine model trained on balanced classes, which achieved a recall of 0.38. This is because the bookmaker's model predicted less than 1% of all actual draws, whereas the support vector machine was able to predict 38% of them in the test set.

Figure 5.1 shows comparisons between the models produced in this study against models that arose from the literature review. We can see that Bilek and Ulas's decision trees achieved, by a significant margin, the highest accuracy scores with a score of 64.8%. Their decision tree model was trained on data from the 2017-2018 season and found that scoring first was the most influential factor on match outcome, whilst the influence of other factors like shots, shots on target and possession percentage depended on the quality of the opposition (Bilek and Ulas 2019). One of the main reasons for the difference between the accuracy scores of their model (0.648) and the model put forward in this study (0.5006) was that their model

Figure 5.1: Bar chart of accuracy scores achieved by the different models

looked to predict the outcome of a match after it had already been played. Their aim was to reverse engineer what factors most affect the outcome of matches, so teams can tailor coaching to maximise their chances of winning, whereas our study looked to create predictive models based purely on statistics available before the match was played. This is why the difference between both models accuracy figures is so great.

Cui et al. achieved a model accuracy of 0.56 on their test using a genetic programming solution. They trained their model using data from the 2011/2012 and part of the 2012/2013 English Premier League season using features like points earned over the last five matches, average goals scored and average goals conceded (Cui et al. 2013). Their accuracy was higher than any of the models produced in this study, which might suggest that more complex models are better at predicting the outcome of football matches when compared to the simpler models produced in this study.

Joseph, Fenton and Neil's model, which included K-Nearest Neighbour as a classifier, achieved an overall average accuracy of 0.5058. The model was trained on data from the 1995/1996 and 1996/1997 season and looked to predict the outcomes of matches played by a single team, Tottenham Hotspur (Joseph, Fenton, and Neil 2006). Their overall accuracy average for their K-Nearest neighbour model was very similar to the K-Nearest Neighbour model produced in this study (0.5085), despite the model in this study being trained on data from every match in five seasons across five leagues. This would suggest that after a certain number of observations, K-Nearest Neighbour's accuracy only improves minimally.

The random forest model produced by Haruna et al. achieved an accuracy of 0.4947. It

was trained on a single season of English premier League data and applied to another, with features including player names, goal difference, home team and away team (Haruna et al. 2021). The Random Forest model covered in this study has a slightly higher accuracy (0.5006) compared to the model that they put forward. Similar to the K-Nearest Neighbour model, this suggests that improving the number of observations in the training data improves the accuracy only very minimally.

Although it may look like a lot of the models that were developed as part of this study performed worse than those in the literature review, we have to take into account the metric used to compare them. We used accuracy to compare the models created for this study to those in the literature, as an F1 score was not available for all of the models in the literature. As discussed previously, this does mean the comparisons we have drawn should be treated reservedly as accuracy is not always the best measure for data with a class imbalance and the accuracy scores may be higher for those models trained on data with a greater class imbalance. This means that whilst it looks like our models performed worse because of lower accuracy scores, they may arguably be better models. If we review the support vector machine models trained on data with balanced classes, the model had the lowest accuracy score of all our models but the highest F1 score. As the F1 score takes into account both precision and recall, it suggests that despite the low score for accuracy the support vector machine trained on balanced data was a better and more rounded model. Unfortunately due to this information being omitted from other studies, this type of analysis was possible.

5.2 Limitations

One of the limitations of the study was the public availability of useful match-level data. The data collected for this project was gathered via fbref's API using the WorldFootballR package in R. Collecting the data for five leagues over five seasons was quite time consuming and, due to recent changes to how their website deals with API, could possibly take longer in the future. Another challenge was that the data needed to engineer the key features in the models (like expected goals) were only available from 2017 onwards, so it would be hard to get additional data to train the model further without subsequent seasons playing out. Other sources of match-level data, either gathered from other databases or through web-scraping, were also unable to reliably provide these figures. Again this leaves the research slightly

hamstrung as you are training models with either more observations but sub-par or less reliable data, or training them with less observations but more detailed data.

This research also worked on two key assumptions:

1. you can predict the outcome of matches in a season using a model trained on data from previous seasons.
2. you can predict the outcome of matches in a league using a model trained on data from different leagues.

This study appears to show that this is possible, but it might have been by chance that those leagues over those seasons were comparable enough that you were able to train a model using that data.

Despite being able to predict results, the research in this paper does very little to further our understanding of the sport and what makes some teams more successful than others. The two main statistics used to engineer features in this paper's models were historic results (previous five results for form and results across the period for team strength) and expected goals (a measure of shot quality). Ultimately, this means our models were built around the notion that teams who win games are more likely to win more games in the future and teams who take better quality shots and concede as few quality shots as possible are more likely to win. Whilst these statistics may be helpful in building models that are both simple and interpretable, it does not help teams understand the mechanics around these two statistics - how do we create better quality shots, what can we do to force our opponent to take shots of a lesser quality and what can we do to win more games.

5.3 Future work

Building upon this study, future research could look to improve upon this study in one of two ways:

1. in the building and training of machine learning models
2. in the application of these models

Research could be undertaken to see if the models in this study could be improved upon by employing additional machine learning techniques like artificial neural networks or genetic

algorithms - Cui et al have already demonstrated some success with genetic programming - to see how their performance compared against the models in this study. If the data was of high enough quality, new and existing models could be trained using more leagues and over a greater number of seasons to see if additional observations affect the different models performance. The comparison between Joseph, Fenton and Neil's research and this study would suggest that this might not be the case, but it could simply be that the results of Tottenham Hotspur were much more predictable between the two seasons stretching 1995 and 1997. The main metric used in this study's models to distinguish attacking and defensive abilities was expected goals. Other research could be undertaken to see if there are other more suitable metrics for quantifying attacking and defensive abilities.

Additional studies could look to see how the model performed when applied to other competitions. The models in this study were trained and tested on top-flight domestic league competitions, but future work could explore how these models perform on cup competitions or international matches. Comparisons could be made to models trained on data from the previous competition, where there are less observations but the model might be more applicable, and models trained on league competitions where there are more observations but the model might be less applicable to cup competitions.

Match data fields

This following table describes the metadata of the match-level dataset once all pre-processing had been done. This dataset was used for the exploratory data analysis.

Table A.1: Metadata for bookmaker's odds data

Variable Name	Variable Type	Variable Description
League	Character	Variable describing the league in which the match was played
Match_Date	Date	Variable describing the day in which the match was played
Home_Team	Character	Variable describing the home team of the match
Home_Score	Numeric	Variable describing the number of goals the home team scored in the match
Home_xG	Numeric	Variable describing the number of expected goals the home team had in the match
Away_Team	Character	Variable describing the away team of the match
Away_Score	Numeric	Variable describing the number of goals the away team scored in the match

Continued on next page

Table A.1: Metadata for bookmaker's odds data (Continued)

Variable Name	Variable Type	Variable Description
Away_xG	Numeric	Variable describing the number of expected goals the away team had in the match
Team	Character	Variable describing the team the figures in this row belong to
Home_Away	Character	Variable describing whether the team played home or away
Gls	Numeric	Variable describing the number of goals the team scored
Ast	Numeric	Variable describing the number of assists the team had
xG_Expected	Numeric	Variable describing the number of expected goals the team had
SCA_SCA	Numeric	Variable describing the number of shot creating actions the team had
GCA_SCA	Numeric	Variable describing the number of goal creating actions the team had
MatchResult	Character	Variable describing the whether the result was a home win, away win or a draw
MatchOutcome	Character	Variable stating the name of the team which won the match
TeamPts	Numeric	Variable describing the number of points the team earned from the match: 3 for a win, 1 for a draw and 0 for a loss
TeamStrength	Numeric	Variable describing the historic strength of a team. Calculated by summing all of their TeamPts across the data set

Continued on next page

Table A.1: Metadata for bookmaker's odds data (Continued)

Variable Name	Variable Type	Variable Description
Form	Numeric	Variable describing the form of the team. Calculated by summing their TeamPts from the last five matches
Attack	Numeric	Variable describing a team's recent attacking form. Calculated by summing their xG_Expected from their last five games
xG_Conceded	Numeric	Variable describing the xG the team conceded
Defend	Numeric	Variable describing a team's recent defensive form. Calculated by summing their xG_Conceded from their last five games

Prediction data fields

This following table describes the metadata of the dataset used in the machine learning algorithms to predict match results once all pre-processing had been done.

Table B.1: Metadata for the data used in the machine learning models

Variable Name	Variable Type	Variable Description
League	Character	Variable describing the league in which the match was played
Match_Date	Date	Variable describing the day in which the match was played
Home_Team	Character	Variable describing the home team of the match
Home_Score	Numeric	Variable describing the number of goals the home team scored in the match
Home_xG	Numeric	Variable describing the number of expected goals the home team had in the match
Away_Team	Character	Variable describing the away team of the match
Away_Score	Numeric	Variable describing the number of goals the away team scored in the match

Continued on next page

Table B.1: Metadata for the data used in the machine learning models (Continued)

Variable Name	Variable Type	Variable Description
Away_xG	Numeric	Variable describing the number of expected goals the away team had in the match
MatchResult	Character	Variable describing the whether the result was a home win, away win or a draw
MatchOutcome	Character	Variable stating the name of the team which won the match
Home_Team Strength	Numeric	Variable describing the historic strength of the home team. Calculated by summing all of their TeamPts across the data set
Away_Team Strength	Numeric	Variable describing the historic strength of the away team. Calculated by summing all of their TeamPts across the data set
Home_Form	Numeric	Variable describing the form of the home team. Calculated by summing their TeamPts from the last five matches
Away_Form	Numeric	Variable describing the form of the away team. Calculated by summing their TeamPts from the last five matches
Home_Attack	Numeric	Variable describing the home team's recent attacking form. Calculated by summing their xG_Expected from their last five games
Away_Attack	Numeric	Variable describing the away team's recent attacking form. Calculated by summing their xG_Expected from their last five games

Continued on next page

Table B.1: Metadata for the data used in the machine learning models (Continued)

Variable Name	Variable Type	Variable Description
Home_Defend	Numeric	Variable describing the home team's recent defensive form. Calculated by summing their xG_Conceded from their last five games
Away_Defend	Numeric	Variable describing the away team's recent defensive form. Calculated by summing their xG_Conceded from their last five games

Odds data fields

This following table describes the metadata of the bookmaker's odds dataset once all pre-processing had been done.

Table C.1: Metadata for bookmaker's odds data

Variable Name	Variable Type	Variable Description
League	Character	Variable describing the league in which the match was played
Match_Date	Date	Variable describing the day in which the match was played
Home_Team	Character	Variable describing the home team of the match
Away_Team	Character	Variable describing the away team of the match
Home_Score	Numeric	Variable describing number of goals the home team scored in the match
Away_Score	Numeric	Variable describing number of goals the away team scored in the match
FTR	Factor	Variable describing the outcome of the match

Continued on next page

Table C.1: Metadata for bookmaker's odds data (Continued)

Variable Name	Variable Type	Variable Description
B365H	Numeric	Variable describing the odds that the match ends with a home win
B365D	Numeric	Variable describing the odds that the match ends with a draw
B365A	Numeric	Variable describing the odds that the match ends with an away win
B365fav	Factor	Variable describing which outcome the bookmaker believes is the most likely

Bibliography

- Baboota, Rahul and Harleen Kaur (2019). "Predictive analysis and modelling football results using machine learning approach for English Premier League". In: *International Journal of Forecasting* 35.2, pp. 741–755. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijforecast.2018.01.003>.
- Baeldung (2022). *Multiclass Classification Using Support Vector Machines*. URL: <https://www.baeldung.com/cs/svm-multiclass-classification>. (accessed: 22.07.2023).
- Berrar, Daniel, Philippe Lopes, and Werner Dubitzky (2019). "Incorporating domain knowledge in machine learning for soccer outcome prediction". In: *Machine Learning* 108, pp. 97–126. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10994-018-5747-8>.
- Bilek, Gunal and Efehan Ulas (2019). "Predicting match outcome according to the quality of opponent in the English premier league using situational variables and team performance indicators". In: *International Journal of Performance Analysis in Sport* 19.6, pp. 930–941. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/24748668.2019.1684773>.
- Breiman, Leo (2001). "Random Forests". In: *Machine Learning* 45, pp. 5–32. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1010933404324>.
- Chirici, Gherardo et al. (2016). "A meta-analysis and review of the literature on the k-Nearest Neighbors technique for forestry applications that use remotely sensed data." In: *Remote Sensing of Environment* 176, pp. 282–294. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2016.02.001>.
- Constantinou, Anthony C. (2019). "Dolores: a model that predicts football match outcomes from all over the world". In: *Machine Learning* 108, pp. 49–75. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10994-018-5703-7>.
- Cramer, J.S. (2002). "The Origins of Logistic Regression". In: *Tinbergen Institute Working Paper* 119/4. URL: <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.360300>.

- Cui, Tianxiang et al. (2013). "An ensemble based Genetic Programming system to predict English football premier league games". In: *2013 IEEE Conference on Evolving and Adaptive Intelligent Systems (EAIS)*, pp. 138–143. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/EAIS.2013.6604116>.
- Deloitte (n.d.). *Deloitte Football Money League 2023*. URL: <https://www2.deloitte.com/uk/en/pages/sports-business-group/articles/deloitte-football-money-league.html>. (accessed: 14.06.2023).
- Dixon, Mark J. and Stuart G. Coles (1997). "Modelling Association Football Scores and Inefficiencies in the Football Betting Market". In: *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society, Series C (Applied Statistics)* 46.2, pp. 256–280. URL: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2986290>.
- Dormann, Carsten F et al. (2013). "Collinearity: a review of methods to deal with it and a simulation study evaluating their performance". In: *Ecography* 36.1, pp. 27–46. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0587.2012.07348.x>. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1600-0587.2012.07348.x>.
- Dubitzky, Werner et al. (2019). "The Open International Soccer Database for machine learning". In: *Machine Learning* 108, pp. 9–28. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10994-018-5726-0>.
- Dvorak, Jiri et al. (2004). "Editorial". In: *The American Journal of Sports Medicine* 32.1_suppl. PMID: 14754853, pp. 3–4. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0363546503262283>.
- FBref (2023). *xG Explained*. URL: <https://fbref.com/en/expected-goals-model-explained/>. (accessed: 06.08.2023).
- FIFA (n.d.). *FIFA Big Count 2006: 270 million people active in football*. URL: <https://digitalhub.fifa.com/m/55621f9fdc8ea7b4/original/mzid0qmguixkcmruvema-pdf.pdf>. (accessed: 14.06.2023).
- Haruna, Usman et al. (2021). "Predicting the Outcomes of Football Matches Using Machine Learning Approaches". In: *Informatics and Intelligent Applications, Proceedings of 1st International Conference, ICIIA 2021*. Ota, Nigeria, pp. 92–104. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-95630-1>.
- Hastie, Trevor, Robert Tibshirani, and Jerome Freidman (2009). *The Elements of Statistical Learning. Data Mining, Inference, and Prediction*. 2nd ed. Springer.

- James, Gareth et al. (2021). *An Introduction to Statistical Learning: With Applications in R*. 2nd ed. Springer.
- Joesph, Adrian, Norman Fenton, and Martin Neil (Nov. 2006). "Predicting football results using Bayesian nets and other machine learning techniques". In: *Knowledge Based Systems* 19, pp. 544–553. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2006.04.011>.
- Kumar, Jitendra et al. (Jan. 2022). "Machine learning for soil moisture assessment". In: pp. 143–168. ISBN: 978-0-323-85214-2. DOI: [10.1016/B978-0-323-85214-2.00001-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-323-85214-2.00001-X).
- Kursa, Miron B. and Witold R. Rudnicki (2010). "Feature Selection with the Boruta Package". In: *Journal of Statistical Software* 36.11, 1â13. DOI: [10.18637/jss.v036.i11](https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v036.i11). URL: <https://www.jstatsoft.org/index.php/jss/article/view/v036i11>.
- RDocumentation (2023). *preProcess: Pre-Processing of Predictors*. URL: <https://www.rdocumentation.org/packages/caret/versions/6.0-86/topics/preProcess>. (accessed: 13.08.2023).
- rdr.io (2023). *downSample: Down- and Up-Sampling Imbalanced Data*. URL: <https://rdr.io/cran/caret/man/downSample.html>. (accessed: 13.08.2023).
- Reep, Charles and Bernard Benjamin (1968). "Skill and Chance in Association Football". In: *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society, Series A (General)* 131.4, pp. 581–585. URL: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2343726>.
- Rico-Gonzalez, Markel et al. (2023). "Machine learning application in soccer: a systematic review". In: *Biology of Sport* 40.1, pp. 249–263. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5114/biolsport.2023.112970>.
- Robberechts, Pieter and Jesse Davis (2018). "Forecasting the FIFA World Cup - Combining Result- and Goal-Based Team Ability Parameters". In: *Machine Learning and Data Mining for Sports Analytics, Proceedings of 5th International Workshop, MLSA 2018*. Dublin, Ireland, pp. 16–30. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-17274-9>.
- Stubinger, Johannes and Julian Knoll (2018). "Beat the Bookmaker - Winning Football Bets with Machine Learning (Best Application Paper)". In: *Artificial Intelligence XXXV, Proceedings of 38th SGAI International Conference on Artificial Intelligence*. Cambridge UK, pp. 219–233. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-04191-5>.
- Theil, Henri (1969). "A Multinomial Extension of the Linear Logit Model". In: *International Economic Review* 10.4, pp. 251–259. URL: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2525642>.

- Vaswani, Ashwin et al. (2020). "An autoencoder based approach to simulate sports games".
In: *Machine Learning and Data Mining for Sports Analytics, Proceedings of 7th International Workshop, MLSA 2020*. Ghent, Belgium, pp. 51–61. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-64912-8>.
- Zhou, Zhi-Hua (2021). *Machine Learning*. 1st ed. Springer.